

Humanity's Last Hope in the cold and dark death of the universe

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A landscape photograph showing a valley with mountains in the background and a body of water in the foreground. The sun is low on the horizon, creating a bright starburst effect and reflecting in the water. The sky is a deep blue, and the mountains are silhouetted against the light.

Sun is not a suitable star for long term settlement as it is a yellow dwarf which isn't one of the most stable kind of star with only about 5 billion years(5 eons) which is a speck compared to the lifespan of red dwarf which last trillions of years(1000s of eons)

Red dwarfs are good and all but is there anything humanity can do to get few more eons.... Yes there is improving interstellar technology and storing vast amount of energy to last a few eons will help extend it as much as possible.

But to really to extend for at least googol years we need to go back to a famous concept.... The dyson sphere and around a black hole(credit:kurzgesagt) and get it's energy by bouncing a light around the blackhole and getting the high energy light..

And at last after progressing one by one at last we can go with my plan of constructing a huge trillions of miles in radius long sphere of mirror from within so it reflects all the energy within the sphere and possibly keep the civilization alive for googols of eons.

Steps to adapt to the heat death

1. Look for a planet in the habitable zone going around red dwarf star then inhabit the planet
2. Make an energy bank and improve interstellar technology
3. Extract energy from a blackhole and improve interstellar technology more
4. Build a sphere of mirror with almost 100% reflectivity keeping energy within region for almost forever